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Preparation of an efficient catalyst through injection of CuI on modified poly (styrene-co-maleic anhydride) and theoretical investigation of the structural and electronic properties of catalyst

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Abstract

A novel polymer supported [poly (styrene-co-maleic imide) (SMI)]Cu(I) nanoparticles was prepared via in situ reaction of 4-amino-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thione with [poly (styrene-co-maleic anhydride)] (SMA) along with immobilization of CuI. These nano-particles were fully characterized by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy analysis, Xray (EDAX), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) analysis, ¹H NMR and FT-IR techniques. Moreover, the structural and electronic features of metal–ligand interactions in the complex model of polymer-supported copper nanocatalyst were assessed using density functional theory calculations. The catalytic activity of these supported Cu(I) nonoparticles was examined in one of the classiest name reaction so-called “click reaction” which is coined K. B Sharpless for the regioselective synthesis of 1,2,3-triazole derivatives using a multicomponent reaction (MCR) involving benzyl halides, sodium azide and terminal alkynes in water as a green solvent. This heterogeneous catalyst showed excellent catalytic activity and was separated by simple filtration and was used at least in five consecutive runs without a significant decrease in its activity.